

Reactions of Carboxylatoaminocobalt(III) Complexes in Solution

ANADI C DASH^{*a}, ACHYUTA N ACHARYA^a, GURU C PRADHAN^a, NIGAMANANDA DAS^b,
PRAKASH MOHANTY^a and RABINDRA K NANDA^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar –751 004

^bRegional Research Laboratory (CSIR), Bhubaneswar –751 013

Manuscript received 29 January 1993

The investigation of the mechanism of reactions of transition metal complexes continues to be an active and fertile area of research. The knowledge regarding the detailed structures of the reagents, intermediates and the products and relation between them is essential to arrive at any conclusion. Basolo and Pearson¹ reviewed the reactions of metal complexes and emphasised the mechanistic details of different types of reaction. Many other reviews²⁻¹⁰ have also appeared relating to the above aspect. We present here a review of the reactions of cobalt(III) complexes with an emphasis on the work reported from our laboratory. Relevant references in this area reported from other laboratories are also cited wherever necessary. This review focusses attention on (i) acid hydrolysis, (ii) base hydrolysis, (iii) anation reactions and (iv) reactions of coordinated ligands, of octahedral cobalt(III) complexes.

Acid hydrolysis

Acid hydrolysis is the most extensively studied reaction of cobalt(III) complexes which involves the replacement of ligand(s) from the cobalt(III) centre by water molecule(s) and is usually carried out around $\text{pH} \leq 3.0$ in order to suppress the relatively rapid base hydrolysis. The aquation process is acid-catalysed for complexes which possess basic sites in the leaving group for further protonation or have strong tendency to form hydrogen bond.

The aquation (eqns. 1 and 2) of carboxylatoaminocobalt(III) complexes occurs generally via two paths¹¹⁻³⁷: (i) the acid-independent or spontaneous

aquation path (k_1) and (ii) the acid-dependent path (k_2). In k_1 path, the carboxylate ligand, RCO_2^- is the leaving group, whereas, the k_2 path involves a rapid acid-base preequilibrium followed by a slow rate-determining step involving the release of protonated carboxylate ligand (RCO_2H),

The protonated carboxylato complexes have been detected spectrophotometrically in the acid-catalysed aquation of *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2]^+$ ($\text{R} = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3$)¹², the protonation being relatively more favourable for the *cis*-complexes.

Basolo *et al.*^{11,13} observed that the rate constant for the uncatalysed path of aquation of a series of carboxylatoaminocobalt(III) complexes is insensitive to the steric influence of 'R' and increases with decreasing base strength. These observations are consistent with the rate-limiting Co–O bond fission in the spontaneous aquation. The acid hydrolysis study of acetato-, trimethylacetato-, trifluoroacetato⁻¹³ and bioxalato¹⁴-pentaaminocobalt(III) revealed that the acid catalysed rate constant (k_2) follows the sequence $k_2(\text{H}_2\text{OC}-\text{CO}_2^-) \sim k_2(\text{CF}_3\text{CO}_2^-) \ll k_2(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2^-)$. Monacelli *et al.*¹³ suggested that the acid catalysed rate constant is retarded due to the steric influence of the bulkier $(\text{CH}_3)\text{C}-$ group and hence, C–O bond cleavage mechanism is likely

to operate in the k_2 path of trimethylacetato complex. In the aquation of oxalatopentaamminecobalt(III)^{14,15} and *cis*-bioxalato(amine)bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III)¹⁶ complexes, as SO_4^{2-} and HSO_4^- catalysed the aquation of the former complex¹⁷, it has been suggested that spontaneous aquation involves Co-O bond fission, whereas acid catalysed aquation may proceed via acyl cleavage (C-O) mechanism. Dash and Nanda¹⁸ observed that spontaneous aquation rates (k_1) and acid catalysed aquation rates (k_2) for malonato-, succinato-, *o*-phthalato- and *o*-methoxybenzoatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes are not affected by steric influence of the carboxylate ligand and that k_1 decreases with increase of $\text{p}K$ of the carboxylic acid. Hence, they proposed that the Co-O bond cleavage mechanism operates in both k_1 and k_2 paths of aquation of these complexes. However, they have not ruled out the possibility of C-O bond cleavage in the k_2 path for the *o*-phthalato complex.

Studying the aquation of salicylato- and substituted-salicylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes, Dash *et al.*¹⁹⁻²¹ found that the spontaneous aquation rate constants do not obey the usual correlation between the rate and base strength of carboxylate ions and the corresponding activation parameters do not compare well with those for several other carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes. But ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values for salicylato-, acetato-, bioxalato- and trifluoroacetatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes are found to obey the isokinetic relationship $-\Delta H^\ddagger = \alpha + \beta\Delta S^\ddagger$ ²². Therefore, the same rate limiting Co-O bond fission is suggested in the spontaneous aquation path (k_1) for the above mentioned complexes. Dissociative interchange (I_d) mechanism involving Co-O bond fission for both k_1 and k_2 paths for the aquation of *cis*-[Co(en)₂(NH₃)OCOC₆H₃(X)(*o*-OH)]²⁺ (X = H, 5-SO₃, 5-Br, 5-NO₂, 3-NO₂) and *cis* [Co(en)₂(imH)OCC₆H₄(*o*-OH)] ions has also been suggested by Dash and Mohanty^{23,24}. Investigating the kinetics of aquation of the α -*cis*-(amine)-oxalato(trimethylenetetramine)cobalt(III), Dash²⁵ suggested that the lower aquation rate constant for both k_1 and k_2 paths of this complex in comparison

to that for [(NH₃)₅CoO₂CCO₂]⁺ and *cis*-[(NH₃)(en)₂CoO₂CCO₂]⁺ cations is presumably due to steric factors influencing the solvation of the complex ions; Co-O bond cleavage mechanism, however, appears to be valid for the spontaneous aquation paths while C-O bond cleavage may be involved in the acid catalysed paths.

The direct determination of actual point of bond fission within the complex may be ascertained by isotopic labelling method. Aquation of acetato and trifluoroacetatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes²⁶ (at pH = 4.0) in solvent water enriched with O¹⁸ isotope liberates CH₃CO₂H without enrichment with isotopic oxygen (O¹⁸) in the aquation of former complex, whereas it is enriched with O¹⁸ isotope for the latter complex. This indicates that the spontaneous (k_1) path involves Co-O bond cleavage for acetato complex whereas the same for trifluoroacetato complex involves acyl oxygen cleavage. However, the later observation somewhat inconclusive as CF₃CO₂⁻ is found to undergo oxygen exchange under the experimental conditions used. Later, by means of O¹⁸ tracer studies, Andrade *et al.*²⁷ established that Co-O bond fission occurs in the k_1 path of aquation of acetato-, trifluoroacetato- and bioxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes while C-O bond cleavage occurs in the acid catalysed path (k_2) of the activated trifluoroacetato- and bioxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes. The acid catalysed aquation of *cis*- and *trans*-[Co(en)₂(O₂CCH₃)₂]⁺²⁸ showed that the *cis*-complex aquates with retention of configuration, whereas the *trans*-isomers gave 75% *cis*- and 25% *trans*-acetatoquo products. A dissociative mechanism involving Co-O bond-breaking for both the isomers has been assigned. However, such assignment was considered tentative in case of the *cis*-complex as the stereochemical result would not distinguish between Co-O and C-O bond fission. Later, Przystas *et al.*¹² carried out O¹⁸ tracer studies of the aquation of the *cis*-complex which indicated that it proceeds by Co-O bond-breaking. Also, O¹⁸ tracer studies in the aquation of (NH₃)₅CoOSO₂R⁺ (R = CH₃, CF₃)²⁹ indicate that acid hydrolysis of these complexes proceeds essentially by Co-O

(99%), rather than S–O cleavage. Aquation of *cis*-[Co(pn)₂(O₂CCH₃)₂]⁺³⁰ resulted in the *cis*-[Co(pn)₂(O₂CCH₃)OH₂]²⁺ in 100% yield while the corresponding *trans*-complex yielded an equilibrium mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-[Co(pn)₂(O₂CCH₃)OH₂]²⁺ in the ratio 3 : 1. A dissociative mechanism involving Co–O bond-breaking has been proposed for the reaction of both isomers.

Das *et al.*³¹ reported that [Co(en)(mal)₂][−] aquates in acidic solution initially to [Co(en)(OH)₂mal]⁺ and then [Co(en)(OH)₂]₄³⁺. The intermediate (aquo)malonate complex has been characterised in solution. The first step is reported to occur by an acid catalysed pathway while the second step occurs by both acid-independent and acid-dependent pathways. In both the pathways, rate-determining step involves ring-opening of the chelated malonate. Chatterjee and Das reported the kinetics of aquation of malonato- and succinato-bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III)³² and (malonato)bis(trimethylenediamine)cobalt(III)³³ complexes. Aquation of the above complexes proceeds both via *k*₁ and *k*₂ paths. The succinato complex reacts about 300 times faster than the corresponding malonato complex, which is consistent with the rate-enhancement with the increase of the chelate ring size from 6 to 7. A 30-fold rate-enhancement has been observed in the case of [Co(tmd)₂mal]⁺ compared to the corresponding ethylenediamine complex due to increase of ring size of the diamine ligand. Opening of the chelate ring involving Co–O bond-breaking is believed to be the rate-determining step, followed by a much faster entry of water molecules leading to the diaqua product. A similar observation has also been made by Chakravarty and Ghosh³⁴.

Pradhan *et al.*³⁵ recently reported the acid hydrolysis of the complexes of the type *cis*-[Co(en)₂AX]²⁺, where A = CH₃NH₂ or C₂H₅NH₂ and X = HCO₂[−], CH₃CO₂[−]. The acetato complexes undergo acid catalysed aquation at a faster rate than the formato complex. Slight rate-enhancement in going from methylamine to ethylamine has also been noted. The first step of aquation of *trans*-[A₂Co(malH)₂]²⁺ (A = en, tmd) has been investigated by Nanda *et al.*³⁶ The major product in both the

cases is *cis*-[A₂Co(malH)OH₂]²⁺. The activation parameters for H⁺ catalysed paths are comparable to those for the *trans* → *cis* isomerisation of *trans*-[Co(en)₂(OH)₂malH]²⁺³⁷ indicating that the *trans* → *cis* isomerisation actually occurs during substitution. The *trans*-[(tmd)₂Co(malH)₂]⁺ reacts ~ 200 times faster than the corresponding ethylenediamine analogue.

Metal ion catalysed aquation

The role of metal ions in catalysing the aquation of metal complexes is attributable to the stabilities and reactivities of the precursor binuclear complexes (formed by the binding of the catalysing metal ion to a suitable site of the departing ligand of the substrate complex) and the successor complexes. The ability of a metal ion to withdraw electrons from the bonding sites is of paramount importance in this context. Usually the leaving group(s)/atom(s) are halides, pseudo-halides, carbonates, carboxylate, biguanides, etc. Thus, metal ion catalysis of aquation of inorganic complexes has a close resemblance to acid catalysis and may occur in almost all cases where acid catalysis is observed. This is because the metal ions are Lewis acids.

The catalytic efficiency of a particular metal ion is a complicated function of several factors, such as charge, size and ability of catalyst metal ion to bind at suitable substrate sites, relative hardness and softness of various reactants, thermodynamic stability of the binuclear precursor complex, etc.^{38,39}

A common feature of most metal ion catalysed hydrolysis reactions involves rapid and reversible formation of a binuclear species between the substrate and the added metal ion which then undergoes catalysed water substitution as delineated in equation (3),

where R = Co^{III} moiety, e.g. (NH₃)₅Co³⁺; L = suitable bifunctional ligand; and M = added catalyst metal ion. However, as the stability of the binuclear intermediate decreases, the first two steps practically merge to a single step mechanism without a sharp

dividing line. In a few cases⁴⁰, the binuclear intermediate is too stable to be a kinetically active species. Although direct isolation and characterisation of the binuclear complexes (R-L-M) have not been possible, except in very few cases^{41,42}, there have been several reports of spectrophotometric detection and determination of thermodynamic stabilities of the binuclear adducts^{38,43-47} in solution. The L-M bond in R-L-M is often suggested to involve distinct covalent interaction.

The study of metal ion catalysed aquation reactions of octahedral cobalt(III) complexes was limited until the late sixties mostly to halo- or pseudo-haloaminocobalt(III) complexes, the catalysing metal ions being Hg^{II}, Tl^{III} and Ag^I. Metal ion catalysed aquation studies have since been extended to coordinated carboxylates using a variety of catalyst metal ions.

Dash and Nanda¹⁹ studied Fe^{III}, Al^{III} and Ga^{III} catalysed aquation of salicylatopentaaminocobalt(III) ion. They postulated rapid and reversible formation of binuclear species between cobalt(III) substrates and added metal ions, which act as the catalytically active labile intermediate in the aquation of salicylato complex. The catalytic activities of the metal ions were found to follow the sequence : Fe^{III} > Ga^{III} > Al^{III} and are consistent with their thermodynamic stabilities. A dissociative mechanism involving Co-O bond fission has been proposed for the catalysed aquation reaction. The catalysed aquation of (NH₃)₅CoC₂O₄⁺⁴⁴ and (en)₂(NH₃)CoC₂O₄⁺¹⁷ by several divalent and trivalent metal ions have also been studied by the same workers. The catalytic activities of the metal ions were found to follow the sequence : Mn^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} and In^{III} < Al^{III} ~ Ga^{III} < Fe^{III} and again parallel the thermodynamic stabilities of the binuclear complexes. The reactions are presumed to occur via Co-O bond fission. The same workers⁴⁴ also studied the Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and In^{III} catalysed hydrolysis of [(NH₃)₅CoO₂CH₂CO₂H]²⁺.

Dash *et al.*⁴⁸ measured spectrophotometrically the stability constants of binuclear species of iron(III)

with some pentaammine(substituted-salicylato)cobalt(III) complexes. The pK_{OH} (K_{OH} is the dissociation constant of phenolic OH group) values of pentaaminocobalt(III) salicylates and stability constants of their iron(III) complexes are reported to decrease in the order : 5-Br > 5-SO₃ > 5-NO₂. Similar observation have also been made⁴⁹ in the reaction of *cis*-[(en)₂(NH₃)Co{(O₂CC₆H₃(X)OH)}]²⁺ (X = H, Br, 5-SO₃, 5-NO₂ and 3-NO₂) with Fe^{III}, Al^{III} and Cu^{II}. The stability constants of the chelated binuclear species (formed between added metal ions and coordinated salicylates via the free phenate group and the carboxyl group bound to the Co^{III} centre) are reported to vary in the order : Fe^{III} > Al^{III} > Cu^{II}. This observation is also corroborated by other results⁵⁰.

Dash *et al.*⁵¹ showed that the aquation of salicylatopentaaminocobalt(III) complexes are induced by Fe^{III} via a reactive binuclear species [(NH₃)₅CoO₂CC₆H₃(X)OFe]⁴⁺. The aquation rate constants of binuclear complexes are found to increase as the electron-withdrawing effect of the substituents (X) increases. Fe^{III} catalysed aquation of a series of complexes of the type [N₅Co(salH)]²⁺ (N₅ = tetren, trien(NH₃), (en)₂NH₃) have been reported⁵². The catalytic efficiency was found to decrease with increase in the steric crowding at the cobalt(III) centre.

Dash⁵³ reported the kinetics of acid aquation of malonato and *O*-phthalatopentaaminocobalt(III) complexes in the presence of Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Fe^{III}, respectively. No catalysis was observed for the phthalate complex. For the malonate complex the catalytic efficiency of metal ions were in the order : Fe^{III} > Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} and parallels the thermodynamic stabilities of the binuclear species. The binuclear species are reported to undergo dissociation by Co-O bond breaking. The rate of acid catalysed aquation of phosphatopentaaminocobalt(III)⁵⁴ is reported to be retarded by Fe^{III} and the high value of the stability constant (1.8 × 10¹¹ dm³ mol⁻¹) has been suggested to be due to Fe^{III} being chelated by phosphate moiety of the substrate.

Cannon and Gardiner⁵⁵ studied the metal ion catalysed hydrolysis of nitrilotriacetatopentaamminecobalt(III). They reported that the coordinated amino polycarboxylate ligand associates with several metal ions, such as Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} forming highly stable binuclear complexes. However, the aquation of binuclear complexes is extremely slow. Association constants (K_{ML}) of the binuclear species formed by a series of divalent metal ions as also lanthanum, with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{O}_2\text{CCO}_2]^+$ have been re-determined spectrophotometrically at 50 and 60^o⁵⁶. For metal ions of the first transition series an approximately linear relationship between $\log K_{\text{M}}$ and $\log k_{\text{aq}}$ (k_{aq} is the metal ion catalysed aquation rate constant) has been observed.

The Cu^{II} catalysed aquation of *cis*-(diformato)-bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) to *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{HCO}_2\text{OH}_2)]^{2+}$ has been investigated by Dash *et al.*⁵⁷. An inner-sphere binuclear complex, *cis*- $[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}\{(\text{O}_2\text{CH})_2\text{Cu}\}]^{3+}$ in which Cu^{II} is bridged by both the formate groups bound to the Co^{III} centre is presumed to be the reactive species. The *cis*-aquaformate species does not undergo Cu^{II} catalysed aquation. Das and Nanda³⁶ studied the Fe^{III} and Al^{III} catalysed aquation of *trans*- $[\text{A}_2\text{Co}(\text{malH})_2]$, ($\text{A} = \text{tmd}, \text{en}$). In both the cases, the major products are *cis*- $[\text{A}_2\text{Co}(\text{malH})\text{OH}_2]^{2+}$. The metal ion did not efficiently promote the aquation of *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{tmd})_2(\text{malH})\text{OH}_2]^{2+}$, presumably due to an unfavourable electrostatic effect which does not favour appreciably the binuclear complexation.

The formation and dissociation of the binuclear complex by several carboxylatoamminecobalt(III) complexes with metal ions such as Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} has been studied by stopped-flow methods. The active species for iron(III) are $\text{Fe}(\text{OH}_2)_6^{3+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH}_2)_5\text{OH}^{2+}$ and the reaction mechanism is established to be I_{a} for the former and I_{d} for the latter⁵⁸. The reactions of iron(III) with coordinated oxalate, malonate indicate that the deprotonated forms react much faster than the protonated form. From the dissociation rate constant of the binuclear species, it appears that the binuclear malonato species more likely exists in non-chelated form whereas the corresponding oxalato species in the chelated form^{59,60}. The com-

plexation of iron(III) with several salicylatopentamminecobalt(III) shows that the phenol form of the cobalt(III) substrates reacts with Fe^{III} and the binuclear species was about 10^3 times kinetically less labile than the monophenolate iron(III) species⁶¹. Iron(III) appeared to be chelated by the salicylate moiety through the Co^{III} bound carboxylate and free phenol group after deprotonation. The rate parameters are little sensitive to the non-labile amine ligand. The dissociation rate constant of the binuclear species, formed by the reaction of Ni^{II} with phenoxide form of the (substituted-salicylato)pentamminecobalt(III), is weakly sensitive to the pentamine moiety around the Co^{III} centre and decreases in the sequence : tetren > $(\text{en})_2(\text{NH}_3)$ (*cis*-isomer) \sim $(\text{NH}_3)_5$ ⁶². Ni^{II} reacts with (oxalato)pentamminecobalt(III) in an I_{d} process to form a binuclear species which exists in equilibrium between its monodentate and chelate forms, the half-bonded oxalate moiety of the cobalt(III) species acting as a chelating ligand⁶³

Base hydrolysis

The base hydrolysis of carboxylatoamminecobalt(III) complexes have been investigated by a number of researchers^{11,64-89}. It is now clear that the base catalysed substitution of cobalt(III) amine complexes involves deprotonation of a suitably cited amine proton, thereby generating a substitutionally labile amido base which undergo dissociatively activated substitution⁶⁵. The reaction generally follows second order kinetics being first order in complex and hydroxide ion concentration.

The base hydrolysis of carboxylatoamminecobalt(III) complexes of the type $[\text{N}_5\text{CoX}]^{2+}$ (where $\text{N}_5 = 5\text{N}$ donor functions and $\text{X} =$ carboxylate ligand), are reported to be consistent with SN_1CB mechanism involving $\text{Co}-\text{O}$ bond heterolysis. Jordan, Taube *et al.*⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸ suggested that when a carboxylate ligand has a strong electron-withdrawing group attached to the carbonyl centre, as in case of trifluoroacetato-, trichloroacetato- and oxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes, both SN_1CB mechanism involving $\text{Co}-\text{O}$ bond breaking and $\text{C}-\text{O}$ bond cleavage occurred in the base hydrolysis of these type of complexes, the observed rate law being

$$\frac{-d[\text{complex}]_T}{dt} = (k_1[\text{OH}^-] + k_2 [\text{OH}^-]^2) [\text{complex}]_T$$

It is interesting to note that the $[\text{OH}^-]^2$ path disappeared for $\text{cis}-(\text{en})_2(\text{imH})\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4^+$ when the reaction was carried out in 50% $\text{D}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ medium⁶⁹. The solvent effect on the second order path might indicate that in addition to the conventional amido conjugate base mechanism there might be acyl cleavage mechanism operative in this path in which OD^- acts as a better nucleophile than OH^- for the attack at the acyl carbon and the resulting tetrahedral intermediate releases oxalate without OH^- (OD^-) assistance^{69,70}.

From kinetic studies on the alkaline hydrolysis of oxalato-, malonato-, fumerato-, succinato- and maleatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes^{67,71,72}, it was observed that the order of reactivity is oxalate > malonate > fumerate > succinate > maleate. This is in accordance with increase of carbon chain-length intervening between the free and bound carboxylate group. We studied the base hydrolysis of $\text{cis}-(\text{N}_4)(\text{NH}_3)\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4^{2+}$ ($\text{N}_4 = (\text{en})_2, \text{trien}$)^{70,73} and showed that the order of reactivity was $\text{N}_4 = (\text{NH}_3)_4 > (\text{en})_2 < \text{trien}$. Retardation of base hydrolysis rates of oxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) in presence of added anions such as PO_4^{3-} , CO_3^{2-} and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ has been ascribed to the less reactive ion-pair which is supportive of SN_1CB mechanism⁷¹. Similar rate retardation was observed by Monk *et al.*⁷⁴ in the base hydrolysis of acetatopentaamminecobalt(III) in presence of added anions (SO_4^{2-} , dicarboxylates).

Nanda and Mohanty⁷⁵ reported that the base hydrolysis of $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoO}_2\text{CC}_6\text{H}_4(\text{X})]^{2+}$ ($\text{X} = p\text{-OH}, m\text{-OH}$) proceeded via Co-O bond cleavage. For the *ortho*-hydroxy complex an internal SN_2 type attack of the phenate oxygen at the cobalt(III) centre and a second path involving the formation of an amido conjugate base and its subsequent decomposition into product (via Co-O bond fission for both the paths) have been reported. This has been modified in terms of internal conjugate base mechanism (ICB) by us believed to be involved in the base hydrolysis of $[\text{N}_5\text{CoO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(o)\text{OH}]^{2+}$ ($\text{N}_5 =$

$(\text{en})_2(\text{NH}_3)$ (*cis*-isomer), $(\text{trien})(\text{NH}_3)$ (*cis-a*-isomer), tetren ($\alpha\beta\text{S}$ isomer)^{70,76,77} in which the bound phenoxide group of the salicylate moiety generated the reactive amido conjugate base by proton abstraction from the coordinated amine.

Studies on base hydrolysis of $\text{cis}-(\text{en})_2(\text{imH})\text{CoX}]^{2+}$ ($\text{X} = -\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}, \text{O}_2\text{CC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}^{2-}$)^{24,69} revealed that the labilising action of imidazolato species was nearly 10^3 times higher than that of imidazole. The base hydrolysis of the complex occurs through SN_1CB mechanism involving rate limiting Co-O bond fission.

Illuminati *et al.*^{78,79} studied the base hydrolysis of a series of complexes of the type $\text{trans}-(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_6\text{H}_4\text{X})_2^+$ ($\text{X} = p\text{-OCH}_3, p\text{-CH}_3, m\text{-CH}_3, p\text{-Cl}, m\text{-F}, m\text{-NO}_2$) *cis*- and *trans*- $[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{O}_2\text{CAR})]^{2+}$, and *cis*- and *trans*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2]^{2+}$ ($\text{R} = \text{alkyl}$ group) and supported the validity of SN_1CB mechanism involving Co-O bond fission. Carunchio *et al.*⁸⁰ studied the base hydrolysis of *cis*- and *trans*-(diacetato)bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) and presented evidence for the formation of the (hydroxo)acetato intermediate in the first step of the reaction. This underwent stereochemical change (*trans* \rightarrow *cis* isomerisation) in a slower step, which favoured the validity of SN_1CB mechanism. Nanda *et al.*⁸¹ showed that *trans*-bis(Hmalonato)bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) base hydrolyses to *cis*- and *trans*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{mal})\text{OH}]$ via SN_1CB mechanism.

Base hydrolysis of cobalt(III) complexes with chelated ligands has been studied by several workers. Sheel *et al.*⁸² suggested that dechelation of oxalate ligand in the base hydrolysis of $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^+$ was rate-controlling; this is then followed by rapid loss of oxalate ligand, resulting in the formation of a *cis/trans* equilibrium mixture of the dihydroxocobalt(III) species. Farago and Mason⁸³ studied the base hydrolysis of $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^+$ at high $[\text{OH}^-]$ and interpreted the stereochemical change in terms of SN_1CB mechanism. Tracer experiment data⁸⁴ on the alkaline hydrolysis of $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^+$ has been interpreted on the basis that the opening of chelate ring by C-O bond cleavage followed by loss of oxalate by Co-O bond cleavage occurred in the act of base hydrolysis. Recently, Buckingham *et*

*al.*⁸⁵ have reported that $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^+$ base hydrolyses to $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{OH})_2^+$ and *cis*- $[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)\text{OH}]$ to *cis*- $[(\text{en})_2(\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2)]^+$, where two outer oxygen atoms of oxalate are reported to exchange rapidly with the solvent before ring opening. The substitution of oxalate predominantly occurred via Co–O bond cleavage ($\text{S}_{\text{N}}1\text{CB}$ mechanism) path. Carunchio *et al.*⁸⁶ studied the kinetics of stepwise base hydrolysis of (malonato)bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) and reported the intermediate, $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{OH})(\text{mal})$, as the first step reaction product. The formation of the hydroxymalonate intermediate was interpreted by them by $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1\text{CB}$ mechanism. Dechelation of aminoacid ligand⁸⁷ has been observed in the base hydrolysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{X}]^+$ ($\text{X} = \text{glyo}, \beta\text{-alao}$). O^{18} tracer experiment data indicated that 84% of the reaction proceeded via Co–O bond fission ($\text{S}_{\text{N}}1\text{CB}$ mechanism).

Formation of the carboxylatoamminecobalt(III) complexes

Replacement of the coordinated water molecule(s) from the metal centre by the nucleophile(s) is known as anation reaction and is the reverse of the acid hydrolysis reaction,

For a cationic complex it usually proceeds through the formation of an ion-pair followed by interchange reaction (*D* or *I_d*) in a rate-determining step leading to the formation to the desired product⁹¹

The rate expression is given by

$$\frac{d \ln [\text{CoL}_5(\text{OH}_2)^{m+}]}{dt} = \frac{K_{\text{IP}} k_1 [\text{X}^{n-}]}{1 + K_{\text{IP}} [\text{X}^{n-}]}$$

In anionic complex *D*-mechanism is suggested⁶⁷. The value of the limiting rate constant in *D*-pathway is close to that of water exchange rate constant whereas that for the *I_d* pathway should be smaller than the water exchange rate constant. The *I_d* pathway is likely to be sensitive to the charge of the nucleophile but not sensitive to its any other characteristic

properties. However, it is really difficult to distinguish between *D* and *I_d* mechanisms from the kinetic point of view. Although a large number of anation reactions involving cobalt(III) complexes have been reported, we will consider the anation of carboxylate ligands only. Recently, a review on anation reaction has appeared⁹³.

Extensive studies have been carried out on the anation reaction of aquopentaamminecobalt(III) ion with several mono and dicarboxylates^{94–101}. The results of such investigations indicate that the anation with the undissociated acids follows the second order kinetics in which ion-pairing is not kinetically identifiable, whereas the basic forms of acids (i.e. the carboxylate) react to form the corresponding carboxylato complex by an *I_d* mechanism^{102,103} involving considerable precursor ion-pair formation. An interesting feature of oxalic acid anation of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOH}_2^{3+}$ is that a four-centred transition state is visualised which can achieve oxalate anation without Co–O bond cleavage. The reactivity order for the undissociated forms of the above mentioned organic acids is malonic \approx oxalic $>$ formic $>$ succinic \approx acetic $>$ propionic. The anation of aquopentaamminecobalt(III) by hydrogen phthalate and phthalate anion is found to proceed via conventional *I_d* mechanism involving rate determining Co–OH₂ bond fission in ion-pairs formed between the aquo complex and hydrogen phthalate anions.

The anation of *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{NH}_3)\text{OH}_2]^{3+}$, $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOH}_2^{3+}$ by salicylate^{104,105} and the anation of *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{NH}_3)\text{OH}_2]^{3+}$ by oxalate¹⁰⁶ have been studied by Dash and Mohanty. Anation by salicylic acid and oxalic acid were not observed. However, anation by H-salicylate and H-oxalate involves the rate-determining and stereotentative substitution of ligand water at the cobalt(III) centre of the ion-pair according to conventional *I_d* mechanism. The anation of aquohydroxobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) ion by oxalate¹⁰⁷ in basic aqueous solution also proceeds through the formation of ion-pair followed by interchange reaction to yield $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{OH})\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$.

The anation reaction of *cis*- $[\text{A}_4\text{Co}(\text{OH}_2)_2]^{3+}$ ($\text{A}_4 = (\text{NH}_3)_4, (\text{en})_2, \text{trien}, (\text{pn})_2$) with oxalic acid has

been investigated by a number of workers¹⁰⁸⁻¹¹². All studies point to a common mechanism in which the anation of diaquacobalt(III) cation by both oxalic acid ($\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$) and bioxalate (HC_2O_4^-) involves outer-sphere ion association equilibria between the re-acting species followed by a rate-determining outer-sphere to inner-sphere conversion process by an I_d path. The final product is formed rapidly by subsequent chelation. The reaction pathways are given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

A hydrogen bonding interaction has been attributed in the association of oxalic acid with *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2]^{3+}$ ¹⁰⁹. The anation reaction of β -*cis*-(trien) $\text{Co}(\text{OH}_2)_2^{3+}$ by malonic acid has been reported¹¹³. The NO_3^- ion induced anation of $[(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{Co}(\text{OH}_2)_2]^{3+}$ and *cis*- $[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH}_2)_2]^{3+}$ by oxalate has been studied by several workers¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁷. The rate acceleration by NO_3^- has been observed.

Weyh *et al.*^{118,119} studied the anation of α -*cis*-ethylenediamine-*N,N'*-diacetatodiaquacobalt(III) ion by oxalate both in slightly and highly acidic media. They observed that the reactions proceed through the conventional pre-association of the reacting species and subsequent rate-determining substitution involving Co-OH₂ bond fission in a dissociative interchange mechanism. In slightly acidic medium, the geometry of the resulting product changes to β -isomer while it retains the same isomer in highly acidic solution.

Banerjee *et al.*¹²⁰⁻¹²³ investigated the anation reaction of *cis*- $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{OH}_2)_2^{3+}$ by a number of organic acids such as salicylic, phthalic, imidodiacetic, acetic and succinic acids, over a wide range of pH. The reactions with phthalic, imidodiacetic and succinic acids proceed in a single rate-controlling

step owing to very fast ring-closure. However, with acetic and salicylic acids consecutive reactions have been noticed. An I_d mechanism has been suggested for all these systems. Anation reactions of $\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{OH})(\text{OH}_2)^{2+}$ with a series of dicarboxylate anions of general formula $\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n}(\text{COO})^{2-}$ ($n = 0 = 8$) have been reported¹²⁴.

Oxidation of the coordinated carboxylates

Oxidation of ligands coordinated to metal ions is normally influenced by the presence of the metal ions. Depending on the nature of the ligand and the metal ion new reaction pathways may evolve. Oxidation of carboxylates coordinated to cobalt(III) has been studied in a few cases. Saffir and Taube¹²⁵ while studying the oxidation of oxalate coordinated to $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5^{3+}$ moiety observed that the oxidation state of Co^{III} was preserved when two-electron oxidants like H_2O_2 , Cl_2 , etc. were used, but with one-electron oxidants like Ce^{4+} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ (in presence of Ag^+), Co^{III} got reduced to Co^{II} . It follows that two-electron oxidants remove both the electrons simultaneously from the oxalate, thus preserving the oxidation state of cobalt(III). On the other hand, one-electron oxidant removes one electron from the oxalate, while the second is removed internally by Co^{III} , it being reduced to Co^{II} .

Candlin and Halpern¹²⁶ observed the formation of a radical ion during the oxidation of (formato) pentaamminecobalt(III) by KMnO_4 with the formation of CO_2 and $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOH}_2^{3+}$ as the products in two different pathways. In the oxidation of *tris*-oxalato-cobalt(III) by Ce^{IV} , Milburn and Kruszyna¹²⁷ noticed the spectral evidence in favour of the formation of a binuclear precursor complex between the oxidant and the cobalt(III) substrate. The oxidation of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}^{\text{III}}$ complexes of lactate, mandelate and benzilate by Ce^{IV} ¹²⁸ produced CO_2 , Ce^{III} and the respective carbonyl compounds by two-electron oxidation and decarboxylation of the carboxylate ligands. In each case, Co^{III} was reduced quantitatively to Co^{II} by internal electron transfer. The reactions are of the type,

The Ce^{IV} oxidation of bioxalatopentaamminecobalt(III)¹²⁹ in acidic sulphate medium indicated the formation of a precursor complex between the reactants with subsequent production of Co^{II} , NH_4^+ , Ce^{III} and CO_2 . The oxidation of formatopentaamminecobalt(III) by halogens (Cl_2 , Br_2 and I_2)¹³⁰⁻¹³² resulted in the formation of aquapentaamminecobalt(III) as a major product. The oxidative degradation of salicylatobisethylenediamminecobalt(III), $(\text{en})_2\text{CoSal}^+$, by KMnO_4 yielded the corresponding oxalato complex¹³³. Intramolecular electron transfer has been observed in the oxidation of glyoxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) ion¹³⁴ and glyoxalic acid by Ce^{IV} in the presence of sulphate with quantitative production of Co^{II} , CO_2 and formic acid. The Ce^{IV} oxidation of pentaamminecobalt(III) complexes of α -amino acids (glycine, α -alanine; *N*-acetyl- and *N*-benzoylglycine and *N*-benzoylalanine)¹³⁵ also proceeds through two parallel pathways. In one path Ce^{IV} oxidises the NH centre and induces the formation of a radical which in a synchronous step undergoes C–C bond fission yielding Co^{II} to the extent of 20% of $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$. The second one is a major path (~80%) in which the radical reacts again with Ce^{IV} to produce Co^{III} complex of glyoxalic acid. Innersphere reduction of Co^{III} to Co^{II} has been proposed in the Ce^{IV} oxidation of oxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) in HClO_4 acid medium¹³⁶. The coordinated oxalate simultaneously transfer one electron to Co^{III} and another to Ce^{IV} reducing them to Co^{II} and Ce^{III} respectively.

Cu^{II} and Ag^{I} catalysed peroxydisulphate oxidation of glycinate¹³⁷ and oxalatopentaamminecobalt(III)¹³⁸ proceeds through innersphere mechanism with the formation of Co^{II} in both the cases, glycinate ligand being transformed to formaldehyde. The synchronous cleavage of N–H and C–C bonds occurs in the oxidation of some cobalt(III) bound glycine and unbound glycine by potassium bromate¹³⁹, the rate of oxidation being susceptible to the polar influence. The substituents at the α -carbon atom in amino acid reduce the rate marginally while those at amino

nitrogen retard the rate considerably. The decrease in absorbance for cobalt(III) complex at 502 nm to the extent of 60% of its initial value and the formation of CO_2 and Co^{II} (both 60%) provide evidence for the cleavage of N–H and C–C bonds occurring to the extent of 60% in a nearly synchronous fashion. Oxalic acid assisted enhanced induced electron transfer is observed in the Cr^{VI} oxidation of pentaamminecobalt(III) complexes of α -hydroxy acids¹⁴⁰. Oxidation of formatopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate by Ag^{I} in acidic condition (1 M H_2SO_4 , HNO_3) proceeds with 97% retention of Co^{III} state as $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{OH}_2^{3+}$ or $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}^{n+}$ ($\text{X} = \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ or NO_3^-). A combination of product distribution, Ag^{I} and Ag^{II} concentration dependence and O^{18} labelling experiments indicate the pathway (97%) is oxidation of $\text{N}_5\text{CoO}_2\text{CH}^{2+}$ directly by Ag^{III} produced through the disproportion, $2\text{Ag}^{2+} = \text{Ag}^{3+} + \text{Ag}^+$, in a relatively rapid reaction. Ag^{I} catalysed peroxydisulphate oxidation of a series of complexes, *cis*-(RNH_2)(en) $_2\text{CoO}_2\text{CH}^{2+}$ ($\text{R} = \text{H}$, CH_3 and C_2H_5)¹⁴² shows that the rate is marginally influenced by the nonlabile alkylamine chain-length; the C–H and N–H bonds are unaffected. Ce^{IV} and Mn^{III} oxidation of (malonato/methyl malonato)pentaamminecobalt(III) complexes yield Co^{II} and formic acid as oxidation products in quantitative amounts¹⁴³. The stoichiometry of Ce^{IV} reaction with malonate complex is 5 : 1 and with free malonic acid is 6 : 1. A comparative study¹⁴⁴ of bromate oxidation of cobalt(III) bound and unbound α -hydroxycarboxylic acids, indicates that the Co^{III} centre does not exert significant electrostatic influence on the seat of attack, i.e. possibly the α -C–H bonds. Bromate oxidation of Co^{III} bound and unbound oxaloacetic acid gives similar result with Co^{II} diketosuccinic acid and succinic acid as main products¹⁴⁵.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. M. S. Dash, Dr. B. Mohanty, Dr. N. K. Mohanty, Dr. H. K. Pattanik, Dr. N. Ray, Dr. S. Khatoon, Mr. P. C. Tripathy, Dr. S. K. Mohapatra, Dr. J. Pradhan, Dr. R. C. Nayak, Mr. N. Dash, Dr. P. K. Das, Dr. N. K. Mohanty and Miss R. Das whose persevering efforts have generated the enormous amount of results to write this review.

References

1. F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", 2nd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1967.
2. M. L. TOBE in "Advances in Inorganic and Bioinorganic Mechanism", ed. A. G. SYKES, Academic, London, 1983, Vol. 2.
3. D. A. HOUSE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **23**, 223.
4. M. L. TOBE, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1970, **3**, 370.
5. T. W. SWADDLE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **14**, 217.
6. R. W. HAY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1984, **57**, 1.
7. C. H. LANGFORD and V. S. SASTRI, "Inorganic Chemistry", M. T. Int. Rev. of Science Ser., 1972, Vol. 9, 203.
8. D. A. PALMER and R. VAN ELDIK, *Chem. Rev.*, 1983, **83**, 655.
9. D. W. MARGERUM, G. R. CAYLEY, D. C. WEATHERBURN and G. W. PAGENKOPF, "Coordination Chemistry, ACS Monograph 174", ed. A. E. MARTELL, American Chemical Society, Washington D. C., 1978, Vol. 2.
10. R. VAN ELDIK, "Advances in Inorganic and Bioinorganic Mechanisms", Academic, New York, 1984, Vol. 3, p. 275.
11. F. BASOLO, J. G. BERGMANN and R. G. PEARSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 22.
12. T. J. PRZYSTAS, J. R. WARD and A. HAIM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 743.
13. F. MONACELLI, F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 1241.
14. C. ANDRADE and H. TAUBE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1087.
15. A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 655.
16. A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 2071.
17. A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 298.
18. A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 119.
19. A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 2024.
20. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and H. K. PATNAIK, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1975, **13**, 1324.
21. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and H. K. PATNAIK, *J. Indian Chem soc.*, 1977, **53**, 431.
22. J. E. LEFFLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, **20**, 1202.
23. A. C. DASH and B. MOHANTY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1179.
24. A. C. DASH and B. MOHANTY, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1980, **5**, 183.
25. A. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 94.
26. C. A. BUNTON and D. R. LLEWELLYN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1692.
27. C. ANDRADE, R. B. JORDAN and H. TAUBE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 711.
28. T. P. DASGUPTA and M. L. TOBE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 1011.
29. D. A. BUCKINGHAM, P. J. CRESSWELL, A. M. SARGESON and W. J. JACKSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 1647.
30. S. I. AMER and J. A. MCLEAN Jr., *Inorg Chim. Acta*, 1985, **101**, 1.
31. S. DAS, S. BHATTACHARYA, R. N. BANERJEE and D. BANERJEA, *Transition. Met. Chem.*, 1982, **7**, 249.
32. C. CHATTERJEE and S. DAS, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1986, **14**, 321.
33. C. CHATTERJEE and S. DAS, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1986, **15**, 147.
34. B. CHAKRABARTY and I. GHOSH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 147.
35. G. C. PARDHAN, R. K. NANDA and A. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 905; 1989, **14**, 309.
36. N. N. DAS and R. K. NANDA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 26; *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1990, **15**, 293.
37. V. CARUNCHIO, G. G. STRAZZA and M. PROSPERI, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.* 1974, **104**, 903.
38. C. BIFANO and R. G. LINCK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 908.
39. R. N. BANERJEE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1985, **68**, 145.
40. J. H. WORELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 1699.
41. Ref. 1, p. 1312; S. MUELLER and U. THEWALT, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1989, **44**, 257; B. V. CROOK, H. BOINE, F. F. STEPHENS, M. J. CANNON and R. D. CANNON, *Polyhedron*, 1989, **8**, 2007.
42. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and N. N. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 538.
43. D. LOELIGER and H. TAUBE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1376.
44. A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 2139.
45. J. H. ESPENSON and W. R. BUSHLEY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 2457.
46. R. K. NANDA and A. C. DASH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1594.
47. Ref. 1, p. 153.
48. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and H. K. PATNAIK, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, **28**, 1613.
49. M. S. DASH and A. C. DASH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 571.
50. R. K. NANDA, A. C. DASH and H. K. PATNAIK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 2087.
51. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and H. K. PATNAIK, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1977, **2**, 183.
52. A. C. DASH, S. KHATOON and R. K. NANDA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 997.
53. A. C. DASH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 132.
54. A. C. DASH and M. S. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 605.
55. R. D. CANNON and J. GARDINER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 390.
56. P. B. ABDULLAH and C. B. MONK, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 1175.
57. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and N. N. DAS, *Transition. Met.*

- Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 337.
58. R. E. CONNIK and C. P. COPPEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 6389; F. P. CAVASINO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **22**, 1378; S. GOUGER and J. STUEHR, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 379.
 59. A. C. DASH and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 1265.
 60. N. N. DAS and R. K. NANDA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 29.
 61. A. C. DASH and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 2336; G. C. PRADHAN, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1992, **17**, 104.
 62. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and A. ACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 769.
 63. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and A. N. ACHARYA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 1023.
 64. T. W. SWADDLE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **14**, 217.
 65. M. L. TOBE and E. AHMED, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 2175.
 66. G. H. JONES, R. B. JORDAN and H. TAUBE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 4406.
 67. N. S. ANGERMAN and R. B. JORDAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 379.
 68. C. ANDRADE and H. TAUBE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 1328.
 69. A. ACHARYA, A. C. DAS and R. K. NANDA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 832.
 70. A. C. DASH and M. S. DASH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 2873.
 71. A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **52**, 298.
 72. A. C. DASH and M. S. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 300.
 73. A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 2071.
 74. C. B. MONK, M. B. M. CHAMPBELL and M. R. WENDT, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 1714.
 75. R. K. NANDA and N. K. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 39.
 76. A. C. DASH and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **20**, 4011.
 77. G. C. PRADHAN, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1992, **17**, 443.
 78. G. ILLUMINATI, F. APRILE and V. CAGLIOTI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **21**, 325; V. CARUNCHIO, G. ILLUMINATI and F. MASPERO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 2693.
 79. G. ILLUMINATI and F. MONACELLI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **6**, 2168.
 80. V. CARUNCHO, G. ILLUMINATI and G. ORTAGGI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 2168.
 81. R. K. NANDA, A. C. DASH and N. DAS, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1989, **14**, 261.
 82. S. SHEEL, D. T. MELOON and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 170.
 83. M. E. FARAGO and C. F. V. MASON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 3100.
 84. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and G. C. PRADHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 905.
 85. D. A. BUCKINGHAM, C. R. CLARK and G. M. MISKELLY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 520.
 86. V. CARUNCHIO, F. GIANNETTA and G. STRAZZA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 3025.
 87. D. A. BUCKINGHAM and C. R. CLARK, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1988, **41**, 133.
 88. G. C. PRADHAN, R. K. NANDA and A. C. DASH, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1989, **14**, 309.
 89. R. K. NANDA and N. K. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 198.
 90. R. K. NANDA, A. C. DASH and S. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 227.
 91. Ref. 1, p. 232.
 92. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and P. MOHANTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **50**, 945.
 93. P. BANERJEE, M. C. GHOSH and P. BHATTACHARYA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1988, **91**, 1.
 94. R. VAN ELDIK and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **14**, 78.
 95. R. VAN ELDIK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 8846.
 96. P. R. JOUBERT and R. VAN ELDIK, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1976, **8**, 411.
 97. A. C. DASH and M. S. DASH, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1976, **6**, 1.
 98. A. C. DASH and M. S. DASH, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1980, **10**, 79.
 99. P. R. JOUBERT and R. VAN ELDIK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **14**, 259.
 100. P. R. JOUBERT and R. VAN ELDIK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1817.
 101. P. R. JOUBERT and R. VAN ELDIK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1817.
 102. C. H. LANGFORD and W. R. MUIR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1817.
 103. A. HAIM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 426.
 104. A. C. DASH and B. MOHANTY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 1053.
 105. A. C. DASH and B. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **17**, 296.
 106. A. C. DASH and B. MOHANTY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 1161.
 107. S. C. CHAN and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 1317.
 108. M. B. DAVIES, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 1277.
 109. D. R. STRANKS and N. VANDERHOEK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 2645.
 110. L. S. BARK, M. B. DAVIES and M. C. POWELL, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1981, **50**, 195.
 111. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and N. RAY, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1982, **11**, 213.
 112. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and N. RAY, *J. Coord. Chem.*,

- 1982, **12**, 91.
113. N. RAY, Ph.D. Thesis, Utkal University, 1985.
114. P. M. BROWN and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1872.
115. R. VAN ELDIK and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 1997.
116. M. B. DAVIES and J. W. LETHBRIDGE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 1579.
117. R. VAN ELDIK, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1980, **44**, L197.
118. P. BHATTACHARYA, M. C. GHOSH and P. BANERJEE, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1986, **11**, 76.
119. J. A. WEYH, R. B. MAYNARD and T. J. BAKER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 2298.
120. M. C. GHOSH, P. BHATTACHARYA and P. BANERJEE, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 68.
121. P. BHATTACHARYA and P. BANERJEE, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1985, 130.
122. P. BHATTACHARYA and P. BANERJEE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1985, **58**, 3593.
123. J. A. WEYH, A. K. NEWLUM, T. J. BAKER and T. K. SHIOYAMA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 2374.
124. S. C. CHAN and M. C. CHOI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 1949.
125. P. SAFFIER and H. TAUBE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 13.
126. J. P. CANDLIN and H. HALPERN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1518.
127. R. M. MILBURN and H. C. KRUSZYNA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 1578.
128. E. S. GOULD and V. S. SRINIVASAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 208.
129. R. K. NANDA and N. K. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 522.
130. N. K. MOHANTY and P. C. RATH, *Indian Chem. Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 56.
131. N. K. MOHANTY and P. C. RATH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 26.
132. N. K. MOHANTY and P. C. RATH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **55**, 1027.
133. R. D. GILLARD and I. R. LYONS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 233.
134. N. K. MOHANTY and R. K. NANDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1985, **58**, 3597.
135. K. SUBRAMANI and V. S. SRINIVASAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 235.
136. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and P. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 162.
137. A. C. DASH, P. MOHANTY and R. K. NANDA, *J. Indian J. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 940.
138. A. C. DASH, R. K. NANDA and P. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 11.
139. S. NARAYANAN and V. S. SRINIVASAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 1117.
140. P. KALIDAS and V. S. SRINIVASAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 667.
141. I. I. CREASER and M. J. LANCASTER, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1988, **41**, 1275.
142. G. C. PRADHAN, A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1990, **15**, 160.
143. K. SUBRAMANI, K. R. SANKARAN and V. S. SRINIVASAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 868.
144. K. R. SANKARAN and V. S. SRINIVASAN, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 1903.
145. K. R. SANKARAN and V. S. SRINIVASAN, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 277.